

The Transportation Problem, an Understanding Technique to Implement in Practical Real Life Problems

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ABSTRACT

The transportation problem is the particular linear programming which is associated with the day-to-day activities in our life. It has solving problem on distribution and transportation on research from one place to another, in other word transportation of single product manufacture of different places (supply or origin) to a different warehouse (demand and destination). There are various method to solve transportation problem first we have to find initial basic feasible solution. For the finding we have various methods such that north west corner method, Matrix minimum method, Vogel approximation method etc. we have to find optimum solution by UV method. in this project We have briefly explained. The above said method by some example; one unsolved transportation problem.at the solution has been given.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The transportation problem (TP) is a special class of linear programming problems, which deals with the transportation of a single homogeneous product from several sources (production or supply centers) to several sinks (destinations or warehouses). When addressing a TP, the practitioner usually has a given capacity at each supply point and a given requirement at each demand point. The main objective of TP is to determine the amounts transported from each source to each sink to minimize the total transportation cost while satisfying the supply and demand restrictions. The basic steps for obtaining an optimum solution to a TP are:

Step 1: Mathematical formulation of the transportation problem;

Step 2: Determining an initial basic feasible solution

Step 3: To test whether the solution is an optimal one. If not, to improve it further

1.2. Background of the study

One of the earliest and most abundant applications of linear programming techniques' has been the formulation and solution of the transportation problems as a linear programming problem. The standard form of the problem was first formulated, along with a constructive solution, by Frank L. Hitchcock in 1941, when he presented a study entitled 'The Distribution of a Product from several sources to Numerous Localities'. This paper sketched out the partial theory of a technique foreshadowing the simplex method; it did not exploit special properties of a transportation

problem except in finding starting solutions. In 1947, another investigator T.C. Koopmans, as a member of the Combined Shipping Board during World War II, also presented a study called 'Optimum Utilization of the Transportation System'. This historic paper was based on his wartime experience. Because of this and the work done earlier by Hitchcock, the classical case is often referred to as the Hitchcock Koopmans Transportation Problem. In 1963, linear programming formulation and the associated systematic method of solution were first developed by G.B. Dantzig. The aim of this study is to look principally at a specific type of Linear Programming Problem, known as the Transportation Problem. Transportation theory is the name given to the study of optimal transportation and allocation of resources. The model is useful for making strategic decisions involved in selecting optimum transportation routes so as to allocate the production of various plants to several warehouses or distribution centers. The transportation model can also be used in making location decisions. The model helps in locating a new facility, a manufacturing plant or an office when two or more number of locations is under consideration. The total transportation cost, distribution cost or shipping cost and production costs are to be minimized by applying the model. The transportation problem itself was first formulated by Hitchcock (1941), and was independently treated by Koopmans and Kantorovich. In fact Monge (1781) formulated it and solved it by geometrical means. Hitchcock (1941) developed the basic transportation problem; however it could be solved for optimally as answers to

complex business problem only in 1951, when George B. Dantzig applied the concept of Linear programming in solving the transportation model. Dantzig (1951) gave the standard LP-formulation TP and applied the simplex method to solve it. Since then the transportation problem has become the classical common subject in almost every textbook on operation research and mathematical programming. The transportation problem can be described using linear programming mathematical model and usually it appears in a transportation tableau. Linear programming has been used successfully in solution of problems concerned with the assignment of personnel, distribution and transportation, engineering, banking, education, petroleum, etc. The classical transportation problem is the name of a mathematical model, which has a special mathematical structure. The mathematical formulation of a large number of problems conforms (or can be made to conform) to this special structure. So the name is frequently used to refer to a particular form of mathematical model rather than the physical situation in which the problem most natural originates. The transportation problem is a special kind of the network optimization problem. The transportation models play an important role in logistics and supply chains. The objective is to schedule shipments from sources to destinations so that total transportation cost is minimized. The problem seeks a production and distribution plan that minimizes total transportation cost. The problem can be formulated as the following mathematical program. The function to be minimized (or maximized) is called Objective function. When the linear system model and the objective functions are both linear equations, we have a linear programming problem. Furthermore, LP algorithms are used in subroutines for solving more difficult optimization problems. A widely considered quintessential LP algorithm is the Simplex Algorithm developed by Dantzig (1947) in response to a challenged to mechanise the Air Force planning process. Linear Programming has been applied extensively in various areas such as transportation, construction, telecommunications, healthcare and public services to name but few areas. The simplex algorithm was the forerunner of many computer programs that are used to solve complex optimization problems (Baynto, 2006). The transportation method has been employed to developed many different types of processes. From machine shop scheduling Mohaghegh (2006) to optimizing operating room schedules in hospitals (Calichman, 2005). The transportation method can be used to reduce the impact of using fossil fuels to transport materials.

1.3. TERMINOLOGY

In this section, we augment your operational research vocabulary with some new terms related to **transportation problem** in linear programming.

Origin It is the location from which shipments are dispatched.

Destination It is the location to which shipments are transported.

Unit Transportation cost It is the cost of transporting one unit of the consignment from an origin to a destination.

Perturbation Technique It is a method used for modifying a degenerate transportation problem, so that the degeneracy can be resolved.

Feasible Solution A solution that satisfies the row and column sum restrictions and also the non-negativity restrictions is a feasible solution.

Basic Feasible Solution A feasible solution of $(m \times n)$ transportation problem is said to be basic feasible solution, when the total number of allocations is equal to $(m + n - 1)$.

Optimal Solution A feasible solution is said to be optimal solution when the total transportation cost will be the minimum cost. In the sections that follow, we will concentrate on algorithms for finding solutions to transportation problems.

Main Objectives The main objective of Transportation Problem is to determine the amounts transported from each source to each sink to minimize the total transportation cost while satisfying the supply and demand restrictions.

Basic Steps

The basic steps for obtaining an optimum solution to a Transportation Problem are:

Step 1: Mathematical formulation of the transportation problem;

Step 2: Determining an initial basic feasible solution;

Step 3: To test whether the solution is an optimal one. If not, to improve it further

Mathematical Formulation

The transportation problem can be stated as an allocation problem in which there are m sources (suppliers) and n destinations (customers). Each of the m sources can allocate to any of the n destinations at a per unit carrying cost c_{ij} (unit transportation cost from source i to destination j). Each source has a supply of S_i units, $1 \leq i \leq m$ and each destination has a demand of d_j units, $1 \leq j \leq n$. The objective is to determine which routes are to be opened and the size of the shipment on those routes, so that the total transportation cost of meeting demand, given the supply constraints, is minimized.

The decision variables

shipment is given by $c_{ij} x_{ij}$. Summing over all i and all j now yields the overall transportation cost for all source-destination combinations.

That is, our objective function is:

$$\text{Minimize: } z = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n c_{ij} x_{ij}$$

1.4. The constraints

Considering warehouse i . The total outgoing shipment from this warehouse is the sum $x_{i1} + x_{i2} + \dots + x_{in}$. In summation notation, this is written as since the total supply from warehouse i is S_i , the total outgoing shipment cannot exceed S_i . That is, we must require

$$\sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} \leq S_i ; i=1, 2, \dots, m$$

Again, considering destination j . The total incoming shipment at this outlet is the sum $x_{1j} + x_{2j} + \dots + x_{mj}$. In summation notation, this is written as $\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij}$. Since the demand at outlet j is d_j , the total incoming shipment should not be less than d_j . That is, we must require

$$\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij} \geq d_j ; j=1,2,\dots,n$$

Of course, as physical shipments, the x_{ij} 's should be non-negative i.e. $x_{ij} \geq 0$. Then the linear programming model representing the transportation problem is generally given as

$$\text{Minimize } z = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n c_{ij} x_{ij}$$

$$\text{subject to } \sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} \leq S_i ; i=1,2,\dots,m$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij} \geq d_j ; j=1,2,\dots,n$$

$$x_{ij} \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } i \text{ and } j.$$

In mathematical terms the above problem can be expressed as finding a set of x_{ij} 's, $i=1,2,\dots,m ; j=1,2,\dots,n$ to

$$\text{Minimize } z = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n c_{ij} x_{ij}$$

$$\text{subject to } \sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} = S_i ; i=1,2,\dots,m$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij} = d_j ; j=1,2,\dots,n$$

$$x_{ij} \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } i \text{ and } j.$$

1.5. Network Representation

We represent each source and destination by a node, the amount of supply at source i by S_i , the amount of demand at destination j by d_j , the unit transportation cost between source i and destination j by c_{ij} and the amount transported from source i to destination j by x_{ij} . The arcs joining the source and destination represent the route through which the commodity is transported. Then the general transportation problem can be represented by the network as in the following figure.

Figure 1.1: Network Representation of Transportation Problem

1.6. Balanced Transportation Problem

When the total supply amount is equal to the total demand then this transportation problem is called the Balanced Transportation problem. That is in the balance transportation problem

$$\sum_{i=1}^m S_i = \sum_{j=1}^n d_j$$

where $\sum_{i=1}^m S_i$ is the total supply amount and $\sum_{j=1}^n d_j$ is the total demand amount.

1.7. Unbalanced Transportation Problem

An unbalanced transportation problem is one in which the total supply of the sources and the total demand at destination centre are not equal. This creates the following two situations:

1. When the total capacity of the origins exceeds the total requirement of destinations, a dummy destination is introduced in the transportation table which absorbs the excess capacity. The cost of shipping from each origin to this dummy destination is assumed to be zero. The insertion of a dummy destination establishes equality between the total sources capacities and total destination requirements.
2. When total capacity of origins is less than the total requirement of destinations, a dummy origin is introduced in the transportation table to meet the excess demand. The cost of shifting from the dummy origin to each destination is assumed to be zero. The introduction of a dummy origin in this case establishes the equality between the total capacity of sources and the total requirement of destinations.

1.8. Matrix Terminology

The matrix used in the transportation models consists of squares called "cells", which when stacked from 'columns' vertically and rows 'horizontally'. The cell allocated at the intersection of a row and a column is designated by its row and column heading. Thus the cell located at the intersection of row A and column 4 is called cell (A, 4). Unit transportation costs are positioned in each cell. The availabilities of each source are placed in the last column while the requirements are placed in the last row.

Table 1.2: Matrix Representation of Transportation Problem

Sources	Warehouses					Supply
	1	2	3	4	5	
A	2	5	8	1	9	25
B	5	6	8	7	10	20
C	1	2	5	8	2	10
Demand	16	10	18	12	14	

1.9. Some Basic Definitions

A. Source

It is a location from which shipment are dispatched.

B. Destination

It is the location to which shipment are transported.

C. Unit Transportation Cost

It is the cost of transporting one unit of the consignment from a source to a destination.

D. Feasible solution

A set of non-negative values x_{ij} , $i=1,2,\dots,m$; $j=1,2,\dots,n$ that satisfies the constraints is called a feasible solution to the transportation problem.

E. Basic feasible solution

A feasible solution that contains no more than $m+n-1$ non-negative allocation is called a basic feasible solution to the transportation problem.

F. Optimal solution

A feasible solution (not necessarily basic) is said to be optimal if it minimizes the total transportation cost.

G. Non-degenerate basic feasible solution

A basic feasible solution to a $(m \times n)$ transportation problem that contains exactly $m+n-1$ allocations in independent position.

H. Degenerate basic feasible solution

A basic feasible solution that contains less than $m+n-1$ non-negative allocations

I. Loop

An ordered set of at least four cells in transportation table is said to be a loop provided

- Any two adjacent cells of the ordered set lie either in the same row in the same column.
- No three or more adjacent cells in the ordered set lie in the same row or column.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. LITERATURE REVIEW

The transportation problem (TP) is an important Linear Programming (LP) model that arises in several contexts and has deservedly received much attention in literature. The transportation problem is probably the most important special appears in the applications and also in the simplicity of the procedure developed for its solution. The following features of the transportation problem are considered to be most important. The TP were the earliest class of linear programs discovered to have totally modular matrices and integral extreme points resulting in considerable simplification of the simplex method. The study of the TP's laid the foundation for further theoretical and algorithmic development of the minimal cost network flow problems. The transportation problem was formalized by the French mathematician (Monge, 1781). Major advances were made in the field during World War II by the Soviet/Russian mathematician and economist Leonid Kantorovich. Consequently, the problem as it is now stated is sometimes known as the Monge-Kantorovich transportation problem. Kantorovich (1942), published a paper on continuous version of the problem and later with Gavurian, and applied study of the capacitated transportation problem (Kantorovich and Gavurin, 1949) many scientific disciplines

have contributed toward analyzing problems associated with the transportation problem, including operation research, economics, engineering, Geographic Information Science and geography. It is explored extensively in the mathematical programming and engineering literatures. Sometimes referred to as the facility location and allocation problem, the Transportation optimization problem can be modeled as a large-scale mixed integer linear programming problem. The origin of transportation was first presented by Hitchcock, (1941), also presented a study entitled "The Distribution of a Product from Several sources to numerous Localities". This presentation is considered to be the first important contribution to the solution of transportation problems. Koopmans, (1947), presented an independent study, not related to Hitchcock's, and called "Optimum Utilization of the Transportation System". These two contributions helped in the development of transportation methods which involve a number of shipping sources and a number of destinations. The transportation problem, received this name because many of its applications involve determining how to optimally transport goods. However it could be solved for optimally as an answer to complex business problem only in 1951, when George B. Dantzig applied the concept of Linear Programming in solving the Transportation models. Dantzig, (1963), then uses the simplex method on transportation problem as the primal simplex transportation method. Stringer and Haley have developed a method of solution using a mechanical analogue. May be the first algorithm to find an optimal solution for the uncapacitated transportation problem was that of Efronymson and Ray. They assumed that each of the unit production cost functions has a fixed charge form. But they remark that their branch-and-bound method can be extended to the case in which each of these functions is concave and consists of several linear Segments. And each unit transportation cost function is linear. J. Frank Sharp et al developed an algorithm for reaching an optimal solution to the production transportation problem for the convex case. 13 The algorithm utilizes the decomposition approach it iterates between a linear programming transportation problem which allocates previously set plant production quantities to various markets and a routine which optimally sets plant production quantities to equate total marginal production costs, including a shadow price representing a relative location cost determined from the transportation problem. Williams applied the decomposition principle of Dantzig and Wolf to the solution of the Hitchcock transportation problem and to several generalizations of it. In this generalizations, the case in which the costs are piecewise linear convex functions is included. He decomposed the problem and reduced to a strictly linear program. In addition he argued that the two problems are the same by a theorem that he called the reduction theorem. The algorithm given by him, to solve the problem, is a variation of the simplex method with "generalized pricing operation". It ignores the integer solution property of the transportation problem so that some problems of not strictly transportation type, and for which the integer solution property may not hold be solved. Shetty (1959) also formulated an algorithm to solve transportation problems taking nonlinear costs. He considered the case when a convex production cost is included at each supply center besides the linear transportation cost. Some of the approaches used to solve the concave transportation problem are presented as follows. The branch and bound

algorithm approach is based on using a convex approximation to the concave cost functions. It is equivalent to the solution of a finite sequence of transportation problems. The algorithm was developed as a particular case of the simplified algorithm for minimizing separable concave functions over linear polyhedral as Falk and Soland (1971) presented a branch and bound algorithm to solve concave separable transportation problem which he called it the "Simplified algorithm" in comparison with similar algorithm given by Falk and himself in 1947. The algorithm reduces the problem to a sequence of linear transportation problem with the same constraint set as the original problem. A.C. Caputo. et. al. presented a methodology for optimally planning long-haul road transport activities through proper aggregation of customer orders in separate full-truckload or less than - truckload shipments in order to minimize total transportation costs. They have demonstrated that evolutionary computation techniques may be effective in tactical planning of transportation activities. The model shows that substantial savings on overall transportation cost may be achieved adopting the methodology in a real life scenario. Roy and Gelders (1980) solved a real life distribution problem of a liquid bottled product through a 3-stage logistic system; the stages of the system are plant-depot, depot-distributor and distributor-dealer. They modelled the customer allocation, depot location and transportation problem as a 0-1 integer programming model with the objective function of minimization of the fleet operating costs, the depot setup costs, and delivery costs subject to supply constraints, demand constraints, truckload capacity constraints, and driver hours constraints. The problem was solved optimally by branch and bound, and Lagrangian relaxation.

3. Basic step in transportation problem

The transportation problem has been formulated by various investigators and solved to various degrees. The systematic method of solution was first given by Dantzig. There are many methods of determining an initial basic feasible solution Well-known heuristics are North West Corner Method, Least Cost Method, Vogel's Approximation Method the starting basic solution they produce and better starting solution yields a smaller objective value. Detailed algorithms of these methods are given below:

3.1. North West Corner Method (NWCM)

A particularly simple method of determining an initial basic feasible solution of a transportation problem is the so-called North West Corner Method, introduced by Charnes and Cooper, where the basic variables are selected from the North West Corner (i.e. top left corner). The standard North West corner rule instructions are paraphrased below:

Step 1: Select the north west (upper left hand) corner cell of the transportation table and allocate as many units as possible equal to the minimum between available supply and demand.

Step 2: Adjust the supply and demand numbers in the respective rows and columns.

Step 3: If the demand for the first cell is satisfied, then move horizontally to the next cell in the second row.

Step 4: If the supply for the first row is exhausted, then move down to the first cell in the second row.

Step 5: If for any cell, supply equals demand, then the next allocation can be made in either in the next row or column.

Step 6: Continue the process until all supply and demand values are exhausted.

Example 1: Consider the following transportation problem

Table-1

		Warehouse						Supply
		1	2	3	4	5	6	
Factory	1	7	10	7	4	7	8	5
	2	5	1	5	5	3	3	6
	3	4	3	7	9	1	9	2
	4	4	6	9	0	0	8	9
Demand		4	4	6	2	4	2	

Applying the solution of the **North West Corner Method (NWCM)**, we obtain the following allocations:

Initial Basic Feasible Solution using North West Corner Method

		1	2	3	4	5	6	Supply
1	4	1					1	5
2	7	10	7	4	7	8		6
3	5	1	5	5	3	3		2
4	2		2					2
4	4	3	7	9	1	9		9
4	4	6	9	0	0	8		9
Demand		4	4	6	2	4	2	

Therefore, the solution for the given problem is $x_{11} = 4, x_{12} = 1, x_{22} = 3, x_{23} = 3, x_{33} = 2, x_{43} = 1, x_{44} = 2, x_{45} = 4$ and $x_{46} = 2$.

For a flow of 22 units with the total transportation cost $z = 4 \times 7 + 1 \times 10 + 3 \times 1 + 3 \times 5 + 2 \times 7 + 1 \times 9 + 2 \times 0 + 4 \times 0 + 2 \times 8 = 28 + 10 + 3 + 15 + 14 + 9 + 0 + 0 + 16 = 95$

3.2. Least Cost Method (LCM)

The heuristics we describe for finding an initial basic feasible solution to a transportation problem is called the least cost method. It is also known as Matrix minima Method or Minimum Cost method or Best Cell Method. In this method, the basic variables are chosen according to the unit transportation cost. This heuristics strikes a compromise between finding a feasible solution quickly and finding a feasible solution that is optimal or very close to the optimal solution. Detailed processes are given below:

Step 1: Identify the box having minimum unit transportation cost in the cost matrix of the transportation table. If a tie occurs, choose any one of them randomly.

Step 2: Allocate as many units as possible equal to the minimum between available supply and demand.

Step 3: Adjust the supply and demand numbers in the respective rows and columns.

Step 4: No further consideration is required for the row or column which is satisfied. If both the row and column are

satisfied at a time, delete only one of the two, and the remaining row or column is assigned zero supply (or demand).

Step 5: Continue the process for the resulting reduced transportation table until all the rim conditions are satisfied.

Example.2

		Destination				Supply
		1	2	3	4	
Factory	1	6	1	9	3	70
	2	11	5	2	8	55
	3	10	12	4	7	90
Demand		85	35	50	45	

Applying the algorithm of the **Row Minimum Method (RMM)**, we obtain the following allocations:

Initial Basic Feasible Solution using Row Minimum Method

	1	2	3	4	Supply
1		35		35	70
2		1	50	5	55
3	85			5	90
Demand	85	35	50	45	

Therefore, the solution for the given problem is $x_{12} = 35, x_{14} = 35, x_{23} = 50, x_{24} = 5, x_{31} = 85$ and $x_{34} = 5$.

For a flow of 215 units with the total transportation cost
 $z = 35 \times 1 + 35 \times 3 + 50 \times 2 + 5 \times 8 + 85 \times 10 + 5 \times 7$
 $= 35 + 105 + 100 + 40 + 850 + 35$
 $= 1165$

3.3. Vogel's Approximation Method (VAM)

The Vogel Approximation (Unit penalty) method is an iterative procedure for computing an initial basic feasible solution of a transportation problem. This method is preferred over the three methods i.e. North West Corner Rule, Row minimum Method and Column Minimum Method, because the initial basic feasible solution obtained by this method is either optimal or very close to the optimal solution. The standard instructions are paraphrased below:

Step 1: If either (total supply > total demand) or (total supply < total demand), balance the transportation problem.

Step 2: Determine the penalty cost for each row by taking difference of lowest cell cost in the row and next to lowest cell cost in the same row and put in front of the row on the right. In a similar fashion, calculate the penalty cost for each column and write them in the bottom of the cost matrix below corresponding columns.

Step 3: Choose the highest penalty costs and observe the row or column to which this corresponds. If a tie occurs, choose any one of them randomly.

Step 4: Make allocation $\min(S_i, d_j)$ to the cell having lowest unit transportation cost in the selected row or column.

Step 5: No further consideration is required for the row or column which is satisfied. If both the row and column are satisfied at a time, delete only one of the two, and the remaining row or column is assigned zero supply (or demand).

Step 6: Calculate fresh penalty costs for the remaining sub-matrix as in Step 2 and allocate following the procedure of Steps 3, 4 and 5. Continue the process until all rows and columns are satisfied.

Step 7: Compute total transportation cost for the feasible allocations using the original balanced transportation cost matrix.

Example 3: Consider the following transportation problem: Cost Matrix for the Numerical example

		Destination				Supply
		1	2	3	4	
Source	1	10	2	20	11	15
	2	12	7	9	20	25
	3	4	14	16	18	10
Demand		5	15	15	15	

Applying the algorithm of the **Vogel's Approximation Method (VAM)**, we obtain the following allocations:

Initial Basic Feasible Solution using Vogel's Approximation Method

	1	2	3	4	Supply	Row Pointers				
1		15			15	(8)	(9)	--	--	
2		0	15	10	25	(2)	(2)	(2)	(11)	
3	5			5	10	(10)	(2)	(2)	(2)	
Demand	5	15	15	15						
Column Pointers	(6)	(5)	(7)	(7)		--	(5)	(7)	(7)	
	--	(7)	(7)	(2)		--	--	(7)	(2)	
	--	--	(7)	(2)						

Therefore, the solution for the given problem is $x_{12} = 15, x_{22} = 0, x_{23} = 15, x_{24} = 10, x_{31} = 5$ and $x_{34} = 5$.

for a flow of 50 units with the total transportation cost
 $z = 15 \times 2 + 0 \times 7 + 15 \times 9 + 10 \times 20 + 5 \times 4 + 5 \times 18$
 $= 30 + 0 + 135 + 200 + 20 + 90$
 $= 475$

Applying the algorithm of the **Vogel's Approximation Method (VAM)**, we obtain the following allocations:

Question: 1
 Three warehouse supply five store the table. indicate the cost of shipment per unit between warehouse and store. warehouse capacity and requirement of the store however a major bridge has been damaged preventing deliveries from warehouse A to store 5 previously ware house B to store 2 and form warehouse C to store 4. With base limitation the optimum delivery scheme to minimum cost.

Solution:

Store	A	B	C	Requirement	
	1	2	4	6	75
	2	3	8	7	345
	3	4	3	8	180
	4	4	6	3	90
	5	2	6	5	210
	850	300	450		

Column penalty

2	3	3
2	3	3
2	-	3
2	-	3
2	-	3
2	-	2
4	-	3

The cost = $2 \times 75 + 3 \times 345 + 4 \times 180 + 4 \times 90 + 3 \times 210 + 0 \times 300 + 0 \times 400 = 2635$

Here $m+n-1 = \text{row numbers} + \text{column numbers} - 1 = 6+3-1=8 = \text{number of basic cells}$

This is a non-degeneracy transportation problem.

Now the optimality can be tested with Modi method.

Considering all the costs in basic cells only and using $C_{ij} = u_i + v_j$

1	A	B	C	$u_1 = 2$
2	2	-	-	$u_2 = 3$
3	3	-	-	$u_3 = 4$
4	4	-	-	$u_4 = 4$
5	4	-	3	$u_5 = 2$
D6	2	-	-	$u_6 = -1$
	-	0	0	

$v_1=0, v_2=-1, v_3=-1$

For non-basic cells

1	A	B	C
2	-	4	6
3	-	8	7
4	-	3	8
5	-	6	-
D6	-	6	5
	-	-	-

$\Delta_{12} = C_{12} - (u_1 + v_2) = 4 - (2 + (-1)) = 3$

$\Delta_{13} = C_{13} - (u_1 + v_3) = 6 - (2 + (-1)) = 5$

$\Delta_{22} = C_{22} - (u_2 + v_2) = 8 - (3 + (-1)) = 6$

$\Delta_{23} = C_{23} - (u_2 + v_3) = 7 - (3 + (-1)) = 5$

$\Delta_{32} = C_{32} - (u_3 + v_2) = 3 - (4 + (-1)) = 5$

$\Delta_{33} = C_{33} - (u_3 + v_3) = 8 - (4 + (-1)) = 5$

$\Delta_{42} = C_{42} - (u_4 + v_2) = 6 - (4 + (-1)) = 5$

$\Delta_{52} = C_{52} - (u_5 + v_2) = 6 - (2 + (-1)) = 5$

$\Delta_{53} = C_{53} - (u_5 + v_3) = 5 - (2 + (-1)) = 4$

$\Delta_{61} = C_{61} - (u_6 + v_1) = 0 - (-1 + 0) = -1$

The solution is not optimal since all Δ_{ij} are not zero or positive.

Among the negative Δ_{ij} , the most negative is $\Delta_{61} = -1$. So, loop starts from there or the cell(61) becomes basic

Solution:

- A. determine initial feasible solution using Vogel Approximation method(VAM)
- B. find the optimum solution to the problem solution:for above model

Total requirement = $75+345+180+90+210=900$

Total supply = $850+300+450=1600$

Here total requirement \neq total supply.

So, this is unbalanced transportation model.

As requirement > supply

We have to add a dummy column and against that column let us assign

$1600-900=700$

Hence the modified transportation model becomes

Store

	A	B	C	Requirement
1	2	4	6	75
2	3	8	7	345
3	4	3	8	180
4	4	6	3	90
5	2	6	5	210
D6	0	0	0	700
	850	300	450	1600

Now the model is balanced.

- (a) To determine initial feasible solution using Vogel Approximation method (VAM)

	A	B	C	
1	75 2	4 4	6	75
2	345 3	8	7	345
3	180 4	3	8	180
4	40 4	6	3 50	90
5	210 2	6	5	210
D6	0	300 0	400 0	700
	850	300	450	1600

Row penalty

2	4	-	-	-
4	-	-	-	-
1	1	4	4	-
1	1	1	1	1
3	3	3	3	3
3	3	3	3	3

Add 40 where (+) sign indicated subtracts 40 where (-) sign indicated

For non-basic cells

	A	B	C
1	75 2	4	6
2	345 3	8	7
3	180 4	3	8
4	40 4 (+)	6	3 50 (-)
5	210 2	6	5
D6	0 0 (-)	0 300	0 400 (+)

	A	B	C
1	-	4	6
2	-	8	7
3	-	3	8
4	4	6	-
5	-	6	5
D6	-	-	-

$$\Delta_{12} = C_{12} - (u_1 + v_2) = 4 - (2 + 0) = 2$$

$$\Delta_{13} = C_{13} - (u_1 + v_3) = 6 - (2 + 0) = 4$$

$$\Delta_{22} = C_{22} - (u_2 + v_2) = 8 - (3 + 0) = 5$$

$$\Delta_{23} = C_{23} - (u_2 + v_3) = 7 - (3 + 0) = 4$$

$$\Delta_{32} = C_{32} - (u_3 + v_2) = 3 - (4 + 0) = -1$$

$$\Delta_{33} = C_{33} - (u_3 + v_3) = 8 - (4 + 0) = 4$$

$$\Delta_{42} = C_{42} - (u_4 + v_2) = 6 - (3 + 0) = 3$$

$$\Delta_{52} = C_{52} - (u_5 + v_2) = 6 - (2 + 0) = 4$$

$$\Delta_{53} = C_{53} - (u_5 + v_3) = 5 - (2 + 0) = 3$$

This gives are new initial basic feasible solution

	A	B	C
1	75 2	4	6
2	345 3	8	7
3	180 4	3	8
4	4	6	90
5	210 2	6	5
D6	40 0	300 0	360 0

The solution is not optimal since all Δ_{ij} are not zero or positive.

Among the negative Δ_{ij} , the most negative is $\Delta_{32} = 3$. So, loop starts from there or the cell (32) becomes basic

Add 180 where (+) sign indicated subtracts 180 where (-) sign indicated.

Considering all the costs in basics cells only and using $c_{ij} = u_i + v_j$

	A	B	C	
1	2	-	-	$u_1 = 2$
2	3	-	-	$u_2 = 3$
3	4	-	-	$u_3 = 4$
4	-	-	3	$u_4 = 3$
5	2	-	-	$u_5 = 2$
D6	0	0	0	$u_6 = 0$

$v_1 = 0 \quad v_2 = 0 \quad v_3 = 0$

	A	B	C
1	75 2	4	6
2	345 3	8	7
3	180 (-)4	3 (+)0	8
4		6	90 3
5	210 4	6	5
D6	40 (-)0	300 (+)0	360 0

This gives are new initial basic feasible solution

	A	B	C
1	75	4	6
	2		
2	345	8	7
	3		
3	4	180	8
		3	
4	4	6	90
			3
5	210	6	5
	4		
D6	220	120	360
	0	0	0

For non –basic cells

	A	B	C
1	-	4	6
2	-	8	7
3	4	-	8
4	4	6	-
5	-	6	5
D6	-	-	-

$$\Delta_{12} = C_{12} - (u_1 + v_2) = 4 - (2 + 0) = 2$$

$$\Delta_{13} = C_{13} - (u_1 + v_3) = 6 - (2 + 0) = 4$$

$$\Delta_{22} = C_{22} - (u_2 + v_2) = 8 - (3 + 0) = 5$$

$$\Delta_{23} = C_{23} - (u_2 + v_3) = 7 - (3 + 0) = 4$$

$$\Delta_{31} = C_{31} - (u_3 + v_1) = 4 - (3 + 0) = 1$$

$$\Delta_{33} = C_{33} - (u_3 + v_3) = 8 - (3 + 0) = 5$$

$$\Delta_{41} = C_{41} - (u_4 + v_1) = 4 - (3 + 0) = 1$$

$$\Delta_{42} = C_{42} - (u_4 + v_2) = 6 - (3 + 0) = 3$$

$$\Delta_{52} = C_{52} - (u_5 + v_2) = 6 - (2 + 0) = 4$$

$$\Delta_{53} = C_{53} - (u_5 + v_3) = 5 - (2 + 0) = 3$$

Now all $\Delta_{ij} > 0$

Now we get optimal solution

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Optimal cost} &= 2 \times 75 + 3 \times 345 + 3 \times 180 + 3 \times 90 + 2 \times 210 + 220 \times 0 + 120 \times 0 + 300 + 0 \\ &= 2415 \end{aligned}$$

Hence our starting solution or initial feasible solution which 2635 is not optimal solution.

Hence, the minimum cost from 2635 reduces to 2415 which is optimal or final cost for transportation problem.

Conclusion

In this paper we have explain transportation problem briefly. a problem for the example has been taken and solve by Vogel approximation method for finding initial basic feasible solution and UV method optimum solution. the solution is given.

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